

Supplementary material for: Comment on “A genetic history of the Balkans from Roman frontier to Slavic migrations”: the omitted NorthMacedonia_IA substrate in the 1-source qpAdm screen

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S1 NorthMacedonia_IA samples

The 14 unique NorthMacedonia_IA individuals used here were published in Lazaridis et al. [1]. We introduce this cluster only as an additional 1-source candidate column under the same present-day qpAdm setup documented by Olalde et al. [2]. As noted in the main text, this is not a later or peripheral source but one drawn from the same immediate authorial and evidentiary context as the published substrate set. We do not infer from that inclusion that it is a literal historical ancestor of any modern population. The exact sample IDs assigned to this and the other Olalde-defined source clusters are recorded in `data/cluster_definitions.tsv`.

S2 Strict target panel

The printed local 1-source rows in Olalde Data S2 Table 8 are `Croatian`, `Serbian`, `Romanian`, `Bulgarian`, `Albanian`, `Greek_Macedonia`, `Greek_Peloponnese`, `Greek_Cyclades`, `Cretan`, and `Greek_Dodecanese`. This comment does not relabel those printed rows to nearby public proxies. In particular, it does not treat printed `Serbian` as identical to public `Serbian_Serb`, and it does not collapse the printed regional Greek labels onto broader public labels such as `Greek` or `Cypriot`. The strict public-HO panel reported here therefore consists of the exact public labels `Croatian`, `Serbian_Serb`, `Romanian`, `Bulgarian`, `Albanian`, `Greek`, and `Cypriot`. The retained target panel is shown in Table S1.

Table S1: Exact public AADR Human Origins target labels retained in the strict public-label panel used in this comment.

Target label
Croatian
Serbian_Serb
Romanian
Bulgarian
Albanian
Greek
Cypriot

S3 Right-set composition

The 13-population right-set used throughout this comment exactly matches the right-set used by Olalde et al. [2] for present-day Balkan analysis (Olalde Data S1): OldAfrica, Steppe_BA, EHG, Iron_Gates_HG, Anatolia_N, Iran_N, Iberia_IA, Greece_Minoan, CroatiaMLBA_SloveniaIA, Netherlands_MBA_IA, Steppe_IA, SoutheastTurkey_Byzantine, and Baltic_BA.

S4 Source-cluster composition

Olalde-defined source clusters were reconstructed by individual ID match and are recorded in `data/cluster_definitions.tsv`. The additional source NorthMacedonia_IA is taken with its default AADR label. In the local 1-source part of printed Table 8, the published Bulgaria source column is labeled Bulgaria_EIA; in this repository it is implemented with the public cluster label Bulgaria_IA.

S5 Full 1-source matrix

Table S2 gives the complete 1-source qpAdm p -value matrix for the retained strict target panel. Entries in bold indicate non-rejection at $p > 0.05$.

Table S2: Full 1-way qpAdm matrix for the strict AADR-label target panel plus NorthMacedonia_IA. Rows are the seven exact AADR-HO target labels retained in this comment. Columns are Olalde’s six published 1-way substrates plus the added NorthMacedonia_IA column. Entries are qpAdm p -values; bold indicates $p > 0.05$.

Target	CroatiaSerbia_RomanLocal	Aegean_BA_IA	Albania_BA_IA	Croatia_IA	Bulgaria_IA	Serbia_BA	NorthMacedonia_IA
Croatian	0.002	5.9e-10	5.7e-22	5.2e-05	2.3e-08	7.8e-07	0.607
Serbian_Serb	0.012	3.8e-09	7.8e-32	1.2e-06	4.7e-12	4.7e-07	0.404
Romanian	0.005	7.6e-09	4.8e-21	4.0e-07	3.0e-10	1.5e-09	0.246
Bulgarian	0.002	8.6e-16	1.5e-29	3.2e-08	1.3e-09	7.7e-10	0.669
Albanian	0.040	5.3e-10	5.1e-21	4.4e-08	5.7e-08	5.6e-06	0.971
Greek	0.040	2.7e-15	1.2e-24	1.5e-07	4.5e-15	7.7e-06	0.915
Cypriot	0.010	3.8e-10	3.4e-21	1.1e-06	1.3e-10	3.0e-05	0.667

S6 Interpretive caution

A 1-source qpAdm pass under this right-set is a non-rejection statement, not a proof of continuity. The contribution of this comment is methodological rather than historical: within this strict public-label restatement, it shows that the published local-substrate set is not exhaustive, because an omitted Iron Age Balkan candidate changes the pass/fail pattern materially when inserted into the same first-stage test.

S7 Pipeline reproducibility

The reproducible pipeline consists of the following steps: `scripts/02_build_ind_and_f2cache.R`, `scripts/03_qpadm_run.R`, `scripts/10_figures.R`, and `scripts/11_tables.R`.

References

- [1] Iosif Lazaridis, Songul Alpaslan-Roodenberg, Ayse Acar, Aysen Acikkol, Anagnostis Agelarakis, Levon Aghikyan, et al. The genetic history of the Southern Arc: A bridge between West Asia and Europe. *Science*, 377(6609):eabm4247, 8 2022. doi: 10.1126/science.abm4247.
- [2] Iñigo Olalde, Pablo Carrión, Ilija Mikić, Nadin Rohland, Swapan Mallick, Iosif Lazaridis, Matthew Mah, Miomir Korać, Snežana Golubović, Sofija Petković, Nataša Miladinović-Radmilović, Dragana Vulović, Timka Alihodžić, Abigail Ash, Miriam Baeta, Juraj Bartík, Željka Bedić, Maja Bilić, Clive Bonsall, Maja Bunčić, Domagoj Bužanić, Mario Carić, Lea Čataj, Mirna Cvetko, Ivan Drnić, Anita Dugonjić, Ana Djukić, Ksenija Djukić, Zdeněk Farkaš, Pavol Jelínek, Marija Jovanovic, Iva Kaić, Hrvoje Kalafatić, Marijana Krm-potić, Siniša Krznar, Tino Leleković, Marian M. de Pancorbo, Vinka Matijević, Branka Milošević Zakić, Anna J. Osterholtz, Julianne M. Paige, Dinko Tresić Pavičić, Zrinka Premužić, Petra Rajić Šikanjić, Anita Rapan Papeša, Lujana Paraman, Mirjana Sanader, Ivana Radovanović, Mirjana Roksandic, Alena Šefčáková, Sofia Stefanović, Maria Teschler-Nicola, Domagoj Tončinić, Brina Zagorc, Kim Callan, Francesca Candilio, Olivia Cheronet, Daniel Fernandes, Aisling Kearns, Ann Marie Lawson, Kirsten Mandl, Anna Wagner, Fatma Zalzal, Anna Zettl, Željko Tomanović, Dušan Keckarević, Mario Novak, Kyle Harper, Michael McCormick, Ron Pinhasi, Miodrag Grbić, Carles Lalueza-Fox, and David Reich. A genetic history of the Balkans from Roman frontier to Slavic migrations. *Cell*, 186(25): 5472–5485.e9, 12 2023. doi: 10.1016/j.cell.2023.10.018.